

Engaging the GLAM Sector in a Federal Open Science Ecosystem: The Belgian FedOSC Approach

Abstract for the DHBenelux

(498/500 words)

FedOSC is a two-year project (2024–2026) involving BELSPO and Belnet, together with Belgium's Federal Scientific Institutes (FSIs), to support the development of Open Science and FAIR research data management (RDM) practices across the Belgian federal scientific landscape. These institutions manage both scientific datasets and cultural heritage collections, making GLAM institutions (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums) a key part of the landscape, especially in the Arts and Documentation domains.

While universities are well represented in existing Open Science frameworks, knowledge within FSIs, particularly in GLAM contexts, is less systematically captured due to its embedding in diverse institutional settings. FedOSC therefore focuses on improving the visibility, support, and connectivity of existing knowledge practices.

The project combines policy development (BELSPO), digital services development (Belnet), and institutional engagement across FSIs. A team of five Data Stewards, organised in domain clusters, works directly with institutions, either embedded locally or connected through Single Points of Contact (SPOCs), including data managers, IT staff, collection managers, and researchers. This structure enables direct interaction with GLAM professionals and supports cross-institutional collaboration.

A central challenge addressed by FedOSC is the integration of GLAM data into generic Open Science practices. Cultural heritage data differs significantly from more standardised scientific datasets: it is heterogeneous, historically accumulated, and context-dependent. Rather than fully aligning these data with conventional research data models, FedOSC recognises the specific conditions of GLAM institutions and supports them in strengthening data management within their own contexts [see also Dressen]. This includes improving workflows, documentation, storage, and reuse, while acknowledging that not all cultural heritage data can nor should be treated as research data in the same way as in academic environments. Survey results and follow-up activities indicate limited time and capacity for RDM, unclear responsibilities, and gaps in metadata practices.

To address these needs, FedOSC combines infrastructure development with capacity building. A cross-institutional data inventory is being developed as the basis for a future shared service catalogue. In parallel, Data Stewards provide hands-on support through interviews and guidance, generating structured insights into data types, formats, and reuse potential.

Training activities are designed as spaces for exchange. A growing learning community, supported through mailing lists, online platforms, and events, currently reaches around 200 participants per month. Webinars on Open Science often include GLAM-specific examples, alongside dedicated sessions for GLAM specialists (e.g. on the concept of GLAM data). These activities support awareness of data management and enable translation between different terminologies and workflows across domains.

Technical services form another strand of the project, alongside policy work and community engagement. These include developments around services such as DMPonline.be, where current work and planning address questions of machine-actionability, versioning, modularity, and flexibility to better respond to evolving practices and technologies.

Early results show strengthened cross-institutional connections, particularly within the GLAM community, and a growing shared understanding of data practices. However, engagement remains uneven and depends strongly on institutional support.

FedOSC demonstrates that integrating GLAM into Open Science requires recognising domain-specific practices and supporting them in ways that enhance visibility and interoperability without reducing their complexity.